

Resource efficiency as a system decision

Wood use between technology, market and industrial reality

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The Technological Perspective.

The Industry
Perspective.

Resource efficiency is a system issue, not only an optimisation issue.

EGGER EcoBox

A large, chaotic pile of wood waste and debris, including various sizes of planks, beams, and fragments, some with white or pink paint. The pile is set against a clear blue sky with a few wispy clouds. The text is overlaid on the right side of the image.

Industry uses different efficiency criteria than research measures.

Recycling that sets a precedent

- » With an annual processing capacity of 120,000 tonnes of recycled wood, the EGGER plant in Rădăuți is considered a pioneer in the material use of recycled wood in Romania.
- » Fundamental development work was carried out for this.
- » With success: Today, EGGER is the largest recycler of wood in the whole of Romania.

The Empowering Consumers for a Green Transition (EmpCo) Directive

- » Resource efficiency is considered an explanatory and evidence-based claim under the EmpCo Directive → **Resource efficiency is not a self-explanatory concept.**
- » The EmpCo is a new EU directive (EU 2024/825) designed to protect consumers from misleading environmental and sustainability claims.
- » From **27 September 2026**, businesses must ensure that all claims regarding environmental or sustainability performance are clear, understandable, verifiable and substantiated.
- » **Objectives of the Directive**
 - › Protection against greenwashing
 - › Promotion of transparent and honest product communication
 - › Strengthening consumer confidence at the point of sale

Ecological impact results from the interaction of system-related decisions.

Approximately 80 Mio. EUR
for a new power plant in St.
Johann i.T. featuring a steam
boiler and cogeneration of
heat and power

- » Start of construction: Spring 2024
- » Operational: Q1/2026
- » Generates at least 100.000
MWh/year using biogenic energy
sources

Net Zero
The EGGER Way

A question of chemistry

- » They make up a small proportion of the product and yet bring a large CO₂ load with them – the binding agents in wood-based materials.
- » Thomas Kuncinger, Chemical Engineering Senior Expert, gives an insight into the research and development work at EGGER, clear climate targets, complex challenges and patented successes.
- » Read the whole story in our sustainability journal VALUABLE from page 14.

GOOD TO KNOW: BINDING AGENTS

- EGGER particleboard already consists of up to 90 % renewable raw materials.
- In total, EGGER has already tested over 50 different binding agent systems, each with a variety of options and recipes.
- Plant-based binding agents also have a CO₂ load – and usually not a small one.
- The key criterion for alternative binding agents on the way to Net Zero by 2050: they must reduce the PCF.

The future of resource efficiency in the raw material wood will not be merely decided by the maximum differentiation of utilisation, but by more intelligent decisions at system level under real industrial conditions.